

Reaction of some rices to root-knot nematode

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We screened 26 rices for resistance to root-knot nematode *Meloidogyne graminicola* Golden and Birchfield 1968. Polypots (150 g capacity) were filled with steam sterilized soil (3 loam: 1 sand) and 10 seeds of each rice variety were sown, 1/pot in 3 sets. When seedlings were 5 d old, 200 infective *M. graminicola* juveniles were inoculated in each pot. Thirty-five days after inoculation, the seedlings were uprooted, washed, fixed in 4% formalin, stained in lactophenol cotton-blue, and the number of egg masses per plant was recorded. Varieties with less than one egg mass were classified as resistant and the others as susceptible.

MW-10, Daya, CR190-103, and IR36 were highly resistant (see table). Although earlier reports indicated that Ramsa and TKM6 were resistant, our test at a high inoculum level showed they were susceptible. ☞

Reaction of rice varieties to root-knot nematode, Cuttack, India.

Variety	Mean number of egg masses ^a
MW10	0.6 a
Daya	0.9 ab
IR36	0.9 ab
CR190-103	1.0 ab
Pratap	1.4 abc
Lalnakanda-41	1.5 bcd
IR50	1.7 bcde
Kesari	1.8 cde
TKM 6	1.8 cde
Ratna	1.8 cde
Jajati	1.9 cde
TKM 9	1.9 cdef
Hamsa	2.2 cdef
Rajeswari	2.2 cdef
Kumar	2.3 defg
Rudra	2.4 efg
Jaya	2.4 efg
Sankar	2.4 efg
Sathi	2.4 efg
Akashi	2.4 efg
Suphala	2.7 fgh
OR164-7-1	2.7 fghi
Hema	3.1 ghij
IR8	3.5 hij
Annapurna	3.6 ij
Parijat	4.0 j

^a Average of 3 replications. Separation of means by DMRT at the 1% level.

Soil and Crop Management

Efficacy of slow-release N fertilizers on rice in coastal soils of Karnataka

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In 1984 wet season, we evaluated prilled urea (PU), lac-coated urea (LCU), neem cake-blended urea (NCU), urea supergranules (USG), and sulfur-coated urea (SCU) at 38, 75, 113, and 150 kg N/ha for rice in midland soils of coastal Karnataka. Soil was a fine, loamy, mixed isohyperthermic Ustoxtropept with pH 5.2, 0.99% organic C, 292 kg available P/ha, and 92 kg available K/ha. The experiment was in split-plot design, with N as main plots and sources as subplots. A no-N control was included.

Three 29-d-old IET3232 (medium duration) seedlings were transplanted at 20- × 15-cm spacing on 20 Jan. All plots received 75-88 kg PK/ha at planting. One-half PU was applied at planting and 25% at tillering and at panicle initiation. LCU, NCU, and SCU were applied at transplanting, and USG was applied 8-10 cm deep between 4 hills in alternate rows, 7 d after transplanting. The field was flooded from transplanting to maturity. The crop was protected from insects, diseases, and weeds, and was harvested 6 Nov.

Fertilizer levels, sources, and interactions gave significantly different yields (see table). Yield increased with N level. Slow-release fertilizers performed

Yield response of rice to unburned and burned rice husk

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We studied the effect of unburned and burned rice husk on rice yield in a pot

Influence of N levels and sources on rice yield, Mangalore, India.

N form	Grain wt/hill (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)
No N (control)		
None	12.1	4.0
38 kg N/ha		
PU	13.0	4.3
LCU	13.0	4.3
NCU	14.1	4.7
USG	14.7	4.9
SCU	15.1	5.0
75 kg N/ha		
PU	13.9	4.6
LCU	13.9	4.8
NCU	14.2	4.9
USG	14.2	4.9
SCU	15.8	5.3
113 kg N/ha		
PU	13.7	4.7
LCU	15.1	5.0
NCU	14.4	5.0
USG	15.2	5.1
SCU	17.7	5.9
150 kg N/ha		
PU	14.9	4.9
LCU	15.1	5.0
NCU	15.5	5.2
USG	13.3	4.4
SCU	15.4	5.1
CD (0.05)		
Levels	ns	0.3
Sources	1.2	0.2
Sources at fixed level of N	ns	0.5
Levels at different source	ns	0.5

better than PU at all N levels, with SCU giving highest yields. Yield with SCU or USG at 38 or 75 kg N/ha was similar to yield with PU at 113 or 150 kg N/ha. At 150 kg N/ha, yields with SCU and USG declined. N level did not significantly affect tiller number or grain weight per hill, but sources did. ☞

experiment. Soil was a clay loam with pH 5.6, 1.2% organic matter, 10 ppm Bray P, 2.8 meq available K/100 g soil, and 0.08% N. Treatments of no rice husk (control) and unburned or burned rice husk at 10 t/ha were assigned in a randomized complete block design with 6 replications. Four IR42 seedlings were transplanted in each pot. Water level

was 5 cm throughout the growing season.

Plant height and tillers per pot were significantly higher with rice husk. Thirty days after transplanting, growth response to burned husk was significantly better than to unburned husk (Table 1), perhaps because unburned husk decomposes more slowly. At later growth, both treatments performed similarly. The trend was similar for panicle number, spikelets per panicle, 1,000-grain weight, and grain yield (Table 2). Compared with the control, plants yielded 22% more with unburned husk and 25% more with burned husk. *ℳ*

Table 1. Effect of rice husk on rice plant height and tillering in rice. Sabah, Malaysia.

Treatment	Plant height ^a (cm)			Tillers (no./pot)	
	30 DT	60 DT	90 DT	30 DT	60 DT
No rice husk	20 c	30 b	46 b	15 c	25 b
Unburned rice husk	26 b	59 a	73 a	23 b	50 a
Burned rice husk	31 a	60 a	74 a	30 a	52 a

^a Means with a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level by Duncan's Multiple Range Test.

Table 2. Effect of rice husk on yield components and rice grain yield. ^a Sabah, Malaysia.

Treatment	Panicles (no.)	Spikelets per panicle	1000-grain weight (g)	Grain yield (g/pot)
No rice husk	25 b	58 b	18 b	180 b
Unburned rice husk	35 a	68 a	22 a	200 a
Burned rice husk	36 a	70 a	23 a	202 a

^a Means with a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's Multiple Range Test.

Effect of organic N fractions in submerged soil on rice yield

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Applied N fertilizer becomes part of soil N. Soil N, although modified by applied N, plays the dominant role in N nutrition for rice. In a 1983-84 wet season experiment, we found that hydrolyzable soil N (using 6 N HCl extractant) at 15, 30, 45, and 60 d after transplanting (DT) was positively and significantly related to rice grain yield (see table), indicating that the hydrolyzable soil N fraction is highly important to N nutrition in submerged rice soil. Nonhydrolyzable soil N was negatively related to grain yield at 60 DT. *ℳ*

Relation between rice yield and the hydrolyzable and nonhydrolyzable soil N fractions, Pantnagar, India.

Parameter	Regression equation ^a	<i>r</i> ^b
<i>Hydrolyzable soil N</i>		
15 DT	$Y = 525 + 1.908 X$	0.912**
30 DT	$Y = 1511 + 1.236 X$	0.857**
45 DT	$Y = 1586 + 1.262 X$	0.884**
60 DT	$Y = 1445 + 1.481 X$	0.572*
<i>Nonhydrolyzable soil N</i>		
60 DT	$Y = 5994 - 3.114 X$	-0.553*

^a Y = grain yield, X = respective organic N fraction. ^b Significant 5% (*) and 1% (**) levels.

Effect of onset of monsoon on length of growing season and productivity of rainfed rice in Madhya Pradesh

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In Madhya Pradesh, India, rice is grown in about 4.7 million ha, of which 80% is rainfed. Rice yields are about 1.0 t/ha and depend entirely on the monsoon.

Analysis of 80 yr (1901-80) of rainfall data from Raipur Station showed that the monsoon usually begins 11-17 Jun

on 24th standard meteorological wk. We used daily rainfall data from 1941 to 1981 to determine the probability of early (19%), normal (34%) and late (47%) onset of monsoon.

Rainfed rice depends entirely on rainfall. Length of rainy season determines the optimum duration of rice varieties. From 40-yr data, we calculated the average length of the growing season under early, normal, and late onset of monsoon (see figure) and averaged the rice productivity for the corresponding years (see table).

Data in the table suggest that early duration varieties are best for this area. *ℳ*

Length of growing season under early, normal, and late onset of monsoon in Raipur, India.

Monsoon onset	Recent probability (%)	Av rainfall (mm)	Water availability period ^a (d)			Total growing period (d)	Av rice yield (t/ha)
			Moist I (PE > R > PE/2)	Humid (R > PE)	Moist II (PE > R > PE/2)		
Early	19	1607	7	127	12	146	1.2
Normal	34	1366	14	115	10	139	1.1
Late	47	1044	13	91	14	118	0.8

^a PE = potential evapotranspiration, R = rainfall.

Available soil phosphorus in a rice - wheat rotation after extended superphosphate application

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High yielding rices and improved

management practices have extended rice - wheat rotations to areas with coarse-textured soils and low available P. We found that in rice - wheat rotation, fertilizer P should be applied to wheat rather than to rice, and that if wheat receives adequate P fertilizer over time, P application to rice can be reduced. This long-term study evaluated